

TRANSLATING CONSTRUCTION TERMINOLOGY: PECULIARITIES, CHALLENGES, AND STRATEGIES

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Annotation. This article is focused on the conveying the meaning of construction terminology and their features, challenges and some feasible solution or strategies. The survey shows that translating construction terminology demand or expertise in both linguistic knowledge and architecture or construction field knowledge.

Keywords: construction, architecture, term, terminology, problems, decoding technique.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена передаче значения строительной терминологии, ее особенностей, проблем и некоторых возможных решений или стратегий. Исследование показывает, что перевод строительной терминологии требует наличия как лингвистических знаний, так и знаний в области архитектуры или строительства.

Ключевые слова: строительство, архитектура, термин, терминология, проблемы, методика расшифровки.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola qurilish terminologiyasini tarjima qilishda yuzaga keladigan muammolar va yechimlarga, shu bilan birga uning xususiyatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Izlanishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki qurilish terminologiyasini tarjima qilishda ham qurilish soha bilimi ham lingvistik bilimni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qurilish, arxitektura, temin, terminologiya, muammolar, decoding texnikasi.

Today, architectural sector are accelerating rapidly in our country. At the same time, new terms and expressions are emerging into the Uzbek language from foreign languages related to the fields of construction engineering and architecture. Sometimes we can use an alternative version of such terms in our language, and sometimes we have to use the term itself, which is not an alternative. Therefore, in order to find a solution to such problems, the wide use of world information resources is one of the urgent tasks.

Translators who ensure communication between people of different nationalities have the duty to know the grammar and vocabulary of the languages of translation and also the term underlying each field involved in depth. An optimum level is achieved when translators/interpreters have the gift of putting people at ease and encouraging their contact thanks to an open, natural and totally interactive dialogue, as if there were no more language barriers between them. A questionnaire is organized to reveal challenges among both novice and professional translators.

Briefly, novice 1 indicated that technical terms, particularly medical ones, are the major problems, in addition to the lack of specialty for the interpreter who should not stand for such specialized disciplines. Rather, she should specialize in one sub discipline. Another issue she

points out knowing that there are many people listening to what she is saying and this may lead her to panic and stop interpreting.

As for novice 2 clarified that technical challenges lie in the presence of untranslatable terms. This trend leads individual to feel pressure as well as owing to the idea of being in a booth and the responsibility that it implies. In addition, she believed that the accent of the speaker can also be problematic for interpreters in general and for novice interpreters in particular. Another issue, she added, is memory loss or (blocking). Novice 3 indicated incorrect interpreting of science subjects such as physics and chemistry conferences is due to interpreters' little knowledge of these subjects. He also indicated that lack of attention and concentration are substantial drawbacks while 56 interpreting scientific texts.

The first expert pointed out that the major challenge is the existence of technical terms, acronyms and abbreviations and stylistic forms of scientific discourse. Compared to novices, the accent of the speaker is also effort-taking task for both novices and speakers.

The second expert referred that inadequate language proficiency in L2 related to structures, vocabulary and science register is a major problem. she added, is memory loss or (blocking) when the interpreter loses the ability to remember a certain term while it is on the tip of one's tongue is also a problem that needs to be dealt with if it continues to happen.

Taking all challenges into an account feasible solution can be offered. These include the ability to speak two languages fluently. The interpreter needs to speak two languages fluently. The simultaneous interpreter needs to speak both tongues with native ability. Particularly, specialist knowledge of terms. This is essential for speeches that include a lot of legal jargon, technological references or medical terminology, for example. An extensive vocabulary is a must. Another basic point is active listening skills. Simultaneous interpretation techniques involve listening with all these senses and with full concentration.

This is one of the reasons that simultaneous translators need regular breaks between boots of interpretation. Also, outstanding memories is one of the contributor to convey coherence and clarity. Simultaneous interpreters need to have superb short-term and long-term memories in order to perform effectively. Empirical knowledge of cultural awareness is the key to ensuring that you use the right language and tone to convey the speaker's message effectively to the target audience. Multi-tasking skills, for instance, listening to somebody talk at the same time that you are talking to yourself is not easy. Even before you add in the complexity of the fact that simultaneous interpreters also need to translate what they are listening to. As such the simultaneous interpreter has to be an exceptional multi-tasker. Interpreters develop strategies at various levels to deal with the challenges in interpreting from a given language to another. As a result, conference interpreters' proficiency levels in each language they work in must be quite high, and extensive practice with interpretation between the two languages in the direction or directions they will employ professionally is crucial. Bartłomiejczyk (2006, p.63) argues that "Successful repeated use of a specific strategy leads to its automation. Automated strategic processes reduce the cognitive load of interpreting." She proposes the following definition: "interpreting strategies are methods that are potentially conducive to solving particular problems encountered by interpreters or generally facilitating the interpreter's task and preventing potential problems." A variety of suggestions can be offered to ease the above mentioned difficulties. Novice interpreters and experts gave the following recommendations:

Table 1 The result of the survey:

	Novice 1	Novice 2	Novice 3	Expert 1	Expert 2
Linguistic	Terminology of a certain field particularly medical ones, are the major problems	Technical challenges lie in the presence of untranslatable terms.	-Little knowledge of the subjects -terminology of a certain field.	The existence of technical terms, acronyms and abbreviations and stylistic forms of scientific discourse.	The inadequate language proficiency in L2 related to structures, vocabulary is a major problem
Non-linguistic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the lack of specialized disciplines -there are many people listening to what she is saying and this may lead her to panic and stop interpreting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Being under pressure -the accent of the speaker - memory loss or (blocking) -the idea of being in a booth and the responsibility. 	Lack of attention and concentration	-the accent of the speaker	memory loss or (blocking)

- More proficiency and experience in scientific fields and being up-to date with new innovations and be familiar with the language of scientific context, which mostly dates back to Latin linguistic origins. Interpreters can establish their own glossary for new terms and update their vocabulary in these fields so that they can convey the original message without errors.

- Translator and interpreter have to consult specialized dictionaries, yet still it is not enough because even if we know the term we should refer to scientific resources and check references which could be more helpful than specialized dictionaries in order to interpret the text in its context. Translator could even consult a specialist, take a doctor or physicist as a good example, to gain better understanding of the subject matter,

- Interpreters should be given additional information and explanation, glossing, for instance where necessary to demystify any ambiguous term and statement. Gile (1995, p.23) presents a much more comprehensive list of coping tactics and discusses them in relation to his

translation theory. They fall into three main categories: comprehension tactics, preventive tactics and reformulation tactics.

1. Comprehension tactics are used when comprehension problems arise or threaten to arise. He lists four basic comprehension tactics: delaying response, reconstructing the segment with the help of the context, using the boothmate’s help and consulting documents in the booth.

2. Preventive tactics are used to limit the risks of failure when the interpreter feels that problems are likely to arise due to time or processing capacity pressure. These include taking notes, changing the ear–voice span, segmentation and changing the order of elements in an enumeration.

3. Reformulation tactics are used to eliminate the potential consequences of problems related to production or short term memory. The interpreter also resorts to other reformulation tactics: replacing a segment with a superordinate term or a more general speech segment, explaining (paraphrasing), reproducing the sound heard in the source language speech, instant naturalisation, and transcoding (Ibrahim Alyahar)

Image 1 The type of windows

Old-fashion wooden windows

Glass-reinforced windows

PVC windows

Modern wooden windows

Expected Results and Outcomes:

Fields like architecture and technology are rapidly evolving. Translators should be up-to-date with latest advancements and innovations in various disciplines to accurately translate terms related to new strategies, techniques. Here are some suggested innovative strategies, techniques and methods so as to provide appropriate translation:

First and foremost, using visual aids, diagrams, illustrations, photographs, or 3D models to supplement translated text can help bridge language barriers and provide a clear understanding of architectural elements, styles, and concepts. For instance: source is extracted from “English for construction”.

Secondly, whenever a term has cultural, historical or technical significance, providing contextual information explanatory notes help the target audience grasp the term’s meaning and relevance within its broader context. A source is take from Sharon Heidenreich English for architects and Civil Engineers:

*In every building, there is a relationship between the exterior and the interior. Depending on the type of building, the climate, the surroundings and its purpose, **the shell separating interior and exterior fulfils different functions.** Glass enables the architect to create a visual link, a view from the interior to the exterior and visa versa. **Solid materials, such as brick or concrete, create a visual barrier between inside and out.** Some surfaces can have a repellent character, are intended to emphasize a certain feature or add contrast to a complex arrangement of structures.*

Thirdly, if a direct translation does not exist, finding synonyms, or equivalents, antonyms in the target language that capture the essence of the term. Looking up words or phrases that evoke similar concepts or emotions. For instance, non-fired brick can be translated into Uzbek target language as a “pishmagan g’isht” but we translate thisterms with providing antonymous translation as “xom g’isht”

Adapting to target audience and context, **fourthly**, taking into consideration the proficiency of the target audience in both architecture and the source language ensure that the translator is not only proficient in both languages but also adaptable and flexible in disciplines. A strong foundation in disciplines is crucial for producing accurate translations. Adapting the translation to resonate with the cultural norms and practices of the target audience while preserving the original concept. Principally, an early visit to conferences before arranged time gives chance to get used to the accent of the speaker as well as provides a overall background of the conferences, to relieve the pressure.

Collaborating with architects, engineers, historians, and other subject-matter experts to ensure accuracy and appropriateness. Their insights can help navigate complex terminology and ensure the translation aligns with the industry’s standards. After translating architectural terms, getting feedback from professionals and non-professionals can reveal whether translations are clear, accurate, and effective in conveying architectural concepts. Striving to maintain the integrity of architectural concepts while adapting them for linguistic and cultural differences should accurately represent the original intent of the architect or designer.

Resources such as creating and maintaining glossaries or databases of architectural terms ensure consistency across projects and help other translators and professionals in the field. When faced with terms that do not have direct equivalents, analyzing how similar concepts are described in the target language’s architectural discourse can assist the most suitable translation based on the context.

Relying on decoding technique is one of the urgent hint during simultaneous translation. **Decoding** is recognizing sound-letter relationships Decoding is the process of translating print

into speech by rapidly matching a letter or combination of letters to their sounds and recognizing the patterns that make syllables and words. There is an area in the brain that deals with language processing and does this process automatically. *Surprisingly, decoding technique can be applied to reveal the meaning terms, proverbs as well as sayings from source language into target ones.* For instance, the words such as "broken line, dotted line, curved line, reinforced concrete, high strength concrete, air dried brick. Decoding is a process that involves interpreting and understanding information. While decoding is often associated with the field of linguistic and language processing, it is a concept that can be applied more broadly across various disciplines and contexts. Decoding in language translation is translating text from one language to another involves decoding the meaning and context of the original text and translating it in the target language. There is well-known saying "Actions speak louder than words" that implies what someone does is more significant or revealing than what they say. Translating idiomatic expressions as well as terms can be particularly challenging because they may not have direct equivalents in other languages. A literal translation into Uzbek might be "Harakatlar so'zlardan kuchliroq" However, this direct translation may not capture the full nuance and cultural relevance of the original English phrase in Uzbek. A more contextually and culturally appropriate translation in Uzbek might be "Amallar so'zlardan qadrliroqdir".The Uzbek translation aims to convey the same message as the original English Phrase, emphasizing the importance and impact of actions over mere words. In this example, decoding in translation involved understanding the underlying meaning and cultural context of the original English saying and then translating it into Uzbek in a way that preserves its intended message and impact. Proposed technique refers to the process of interpreting and understanding a text or message that has been translated from one language into another. Translation is not just a matter of substituting words from one language into another. It involves understanding the meaning, context and nuances of both the source and target languages to convey the original message accurately and effectively.

All in all, decoding in translation involves a deep understanding of both the source and target languages, as well as the cultural and contextual aspects associated with the text , to accurately and effectively convey the original message across language barriers.

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